

The Stingless Bee, *Tetragonula minangkabau*, as a Vector for Blood Disease Bacterium, *Ralstonia solanacearum*

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Blood disease is a plant disease suffered by banana plants caused by the bacterium *Ralstonia solanacearum* from phylotype IV. The disease is spread by visiting pollinator insects including *Tetragonula minangkabau*. The stingless bee carries the blood disease bacterium both inside and outside of its body in adult, young insect, and larvae stages from the visit to infected plants. Blood disease in banana plants causes the production to massively decrease in the infected plants (Mairawita *et al*, 2012). There is a need to understand the spread of this disease and its vectors to overcome its bad effects in agriculture. Understanding the spread of *R. solanacearum* using *T. minangkabau* as a vector demands knowledge from both ecology and microbiology.

Western Sumatra stingless bee, *Tetragonula minangkabau*, belongs to stingless bee taxonomic tribe, Meliponini, which itself is within a larger bee family, Apidae. Despite their small sizes in comparison with other bee species, their group is the most speciose among eusocial honey bees. There are between 500-600 species of stingless bee around the world, limited to tropical and subtropical regions as they're active throughout the year. They have a generalist lifestyle, collecting nectar and pollen from various plant species, including many agricultural plants. Their favourite places to house their nests are rock crevices, soil cavities, and wooden houses. Their need for considerable nectar and pollen demands a great number of worker bees. As cold blooded insects, stingless bees are sensitive to environmental conditions such as temperature. Its flying activity is heavily influenced by external environment parameters including rainfall, season, relative humidity, and light intensity (Herwina *et al*, 2021). Daily activity for *Tetragonula minangkabau* starts around 8.00 until 15.00. The peak daily activity for *T. minangkabau* for food foraging happens at 11.00 (Putra *et al*, 2017).

The stingless bee, *T. minangkabau*, is used in the agricultural sector to increase production as it's proven as an effective pollinator for several valuable crops such as banana and chilli pepper. Its colony can be housed in the plantation itself or near it. Perfect pollination that the bees do increases yield, both in quantity and quality. Small size of stingless bees in general made it possible for them to pollinate agricultural crops that most of the time have small sized flowers (Putra *et al*, 2016). This role made *T. minangkabau* a desirable vector for *R. solanacearum* to get into its definitive

hosts. Potatoes, tomatoes, and especially bananas are vulnerable to its infection along with legions of other economically important plant crops. It settles in xylem tissue of the host plant and then proceeds to secrete proteins to lysis plant cells to give it nutrients. As the infection marches on, colonization of xylem by *R. solanacearum* begins to lower production by the host plants and at its inevitable end kill them (Pueymiro & Genin, 2009). For its wide range of host species it infects and devastates, *R. solanacearum* has a high level of diversity to better exploit its host range, epidemiological relationship, and geographic characteristics. This diversity is divided into 4 strains called phylotypes that correspond to their geographical origins, the 4 phylotypes are Asia (I), America (II), Africa (III), and Indonesia (IV). Each strain has developed to attack the economically important crops in their areas (Guarischi-Sousa *et al*, 2016).

Blood disease in bananas caused by *R. solacearum* phylotype IV exposes itself through the symptoms of wilting, red vascular staining especially in xylem part, internal rot, and loss of green pigmentation on banana leaves. As plantation domesticated varieties of banana no longer able to reproduce sexually, they produce clone of themselves asexually resulting in population highly susceptible to mass infection. Blood disease has spread unhindered throughout Indonesia and Malaysia carried by delivered products and insect vectors (Ray *et al*, 2021). Situation outside of Southeast Asia is not much better either. In Africa, bananas makeup significant percentage of the population's daily nutrition intake and South America produces the majority of exported bananas. *R. solanacearum* from phylotypes I and II have ravaged the areas. All of the affected areas have reported reduced production yield and increase in crop disease management. Stingless bees including *T. minangkabau* often visit banana trees to feed on its nectar-like sap. The bacteria exploit this activity to spread themselves by congregating in the sap to wait for a visit from the bee (Blomme *et al*, 2017).

Stingless bees themselves have been found to spread bacterial caused plant disease before the emergence of banana blood disease. They were the primary vector for banana xanthomonas wilt in Africa. Xanthomonas hitchhiker in the bee through the same nectar-like sap produced by banana plants. The infected bee then can carry xanthomonas to its nest where it can jump on more bees and in the end other banana plants (Namu & Wittman, 2014). Members of Meliponini as eusocial insects have behavioural responses toward bacterial disease that worsen their own health and therefore can endanger their colonies such as infection from *Lysinibacillus sphaericu*. Banana blood disease unfortunately doesn't trigger response from the bees as it only uses them to get into other host plants (Shanks *et al*, 2017). This fact makes the search for ways to contain banana blood disease from stingless bee vectors have to come from anthropogenic efforts.

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